

ANALYSIS ON THE FULL SET OF DATA

Number of trials per stimulus mode					
	0	100	140	180	Total
None	82	-	-	-	82
AudioOnly	-	81	87	82	254
VisualsOnly	-	85	83	86	254
Both	-	83	87	84	254
Total	82	249	257	252	840

Stimuli type and performance

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variable: correctNormalized

ANOVA correctNormalized~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
2.007	0.111	

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasStimulusTrial				
mean Has-No	t	p		
0.9985372	1.0105963	-0.79161	0.4306	

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasVisualTrial				
mean Has-No	t	p		
0.9923476	1.0110051	-2.2158	0.02703	

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasAudioTrial				
mean Has-No	t	p		
1.0043961	0.9926743	1.3837	0.1669	

Stimuli tempo and performance

Parameter: tempo | Variable: correctNormalized | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo		
F	p	
1.424	0.234	

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]				
F	p			
2.461	0.0875			

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
0.18	0.835	

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
0.419	0.658	

TukeyHSD				
diff	lwr	upr	p adj	
140-100	0.0191781	-0.0229820	0.0613384	0.5319850
180-100	0.0402257	-0.0025497	0.0830011	0.0702332
180-140	0.0210475	-0.0209793	0.0630744	0.4657003

Stimuli type and time estimation

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception)

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
0.569	0.636	

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasStimulusTrial				
mean Has-No	t	p		
0.0120830	0.0290069	-0.5091	0.6118	

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasVisualTrial				
mean Has-No	t	p		
0.0117994	0.0166969	-0.23071	0.8176	

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasAudioTrial				
mean Has-No	t	p		
0.0205346	0.0035358	0.79259	0.4283	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
0.569	0.636	

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasStimulusTrial				
mean Has-No	t	p		
0.2202785	0.2131982	0.31973	0.7498	

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasVisualTrial				
mean Has-No	t	p		
0.2206991	0.2178860	0.19309	0.8469	

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasAudioTrial				
mean Has-No	t	p		
0.2190183	0.2204408	-0.095811	0.9237	

Stimuli tempo and time estimation

Parameter: tempo | Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception) | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo		
F	p	
2.328	0.0732	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]				
F	p			
3.288	0.039			

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
0.706	0.495	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
1.546	0.215	

TUKEY HSD				
diff	lwr	upr	p adj	
100-0	-0.004345989	-0.1042085	0.0955166	0.9994969
140-0	-0.056169693	-0.1556464	0.0433071	0.4663147
180-0	0.010672619	-0.0890426	0.1103878	0.9926922
140-100	-0.051823703	-0.1215673	0.0179199	0.2233741
180-100	0.015018609	-0.0550646	0.0851018	0.9461046
180-140	0.066842312	-0.0026901	0.1363747	0.0646654

TUKEY HSD				
diff	lwr	upr	p adj	
140-100	-0.1060294	-0.2123215	0.0002625	0.0507285
180-100	-0.0147473	-0.1225906	0.0930957	0.9443150
180-140	0.0912820	-0.0146738	0.1972379	0.1068760

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo		
F	p	
0.784	0.503	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]				
F	p			
0.861	0.424			

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
0.113	0.893	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
0.113	0.893	

Stimuli type and time judgment

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variable: reportedSpeedPerception

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~classes			
chi-2	df	p	
10.267	0.569	0.01643	

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasStimulusTrial				
W	p			
36984	0.003205			
mean Has	mean Not			
3.452507	3.073171			

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasAudioTrial				
W	p			
87943	0.3227			
mean Has	mean Not			
3.446429	3.369048			

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasVisualTrial				
W	p			
91847	0.02273			
mean Has	mean Not			
3.480315	3.316265			

paired WILCOXON			
AudioOnly	Both	None	
Both	0.321	-	-
None	0.048	0.015	-
VisualsOnly	0.489	0.650	0.015

Stimuli tempo and time judgment

Parameter: tempo | Variable: reportedSpeedPerception | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo			
chi-2	df	p	
15.432	3	0.001482	

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]				
chi-2	df	p		
3.8335	2	0.1471		

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]			
chi-2	df	p	
0.03274	2	0.9838	

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterBOTH]			
chi-2	df	p	
7.2343	2	0.02686	

	0	100	140
100	0.1174	-	-
140	0.0063	0.0642	-
180	0.0053	0.0305	0.6510

	100	140
140	0.091	-
180	0.032	0.358

Correlations time judgment - estimation - performance

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), reportedSpeedPerception, correctNormalized

PEARSON deltaTimePerception~correctNormalized			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.10989722	0.0251443	-0.0425708	0.2177

PEARSON abs(deltaTimePerception)~correctNormalized			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.1498825	-0.0155265	-0.0830820	0.01602

SPEARMAN deltaTimePerception~reportedSpeedPerception			
rho	p		
-0.2505479	1.724e-13		

SPEARMAN abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedSpeedPerception			
rho	p		
0.1065027	0.001995		

SPEARMAN correctNormalized~reportedSpeedPerception			
rho	p		
0.1499229	1.265e-05		

Confounding effects of fatigue

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), reportedSpeedPerception, correctNormalized, reportedFatigue

ANOVA correctNormalized~reportedFatigue		
F	p	
14.56	1.68e-11	

Anova deltaTimePerception~reportedFatigue		
F	p	
3.86	0.00409	

Anova abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedFatigue		
F	p	
0.277	0.893	

TUKEY HSD				
diff	lwr	upr	p adj	
2-1	0.03074690	-0.0212543	0.0827481	0.4872362
3-1	0.086703629	0.0380559	0.1353513	0.0000130
4-1	0.092614421	0.0440903	0.1411385	0.0000023
5-1	0.100818590	0.0521066	0.1495305	0.0000002
3-2	0.055956727	0.0207089	0.0912045	0.0001555
4-2	0.061867519	0.0267904	0.0969443	0.0000167
5-2	0.070071689	0.0347352	0.1054081	0.0000008
4-3	0.005910792	-0.0239700	0.0357916	0.9830424
5-3	0.014114962	-0.0160699	0.0442999	0.7046637
5-4	0.008204170	-0.0217811	0.0381894	0.9450188

TUKEY HSD				
diff	lwr	upr	p adj	
2-1	-0.1045315	-0.2412166	0.0321536	0.2250073
3-1	0.0274508	-0.1004752	0.1553769	0.9770665
4-1	-0.0152086	-0.1427540	0.1123367	0.9975599
5-1	-0.0104268	-0.1384660	0.1176121	0.9994550
3-2	0.1319823	0.0392565	0.2247081	0.0010188
4-2	0.0893228	-0.0028769	0.1815226	0.0628239
5-2	0.0941046	0.0012229	0.1869863	0.0452922
4-3	-0.0426594	-0.1212919	0.0359730	0.5737846
5-3	-0.0378777	-0.1173086	0.0415531	0.6890479
5-4	0.0047817	-0.0740345	0.0835980	0.9998304

Spearman correctNormalized~reportedFatigue		
rho	p	
0.1897809	2.924e-08	

Spearman deltaTimePerception~reportedFatigue		
rho	p	
0.0450799	0.1918	

Spearman abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedFatigue		
rho	p	
0.1065027	0.8419	

Spearman reportedSpeedPerception~reportedFatigue		
rho	p	
0.2267418	2.88e-11	

Confounding effects of trial index

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), correctNormalized, trialIndex

Pearson correctNormalized~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
0.1943050	0.3205131	0.2585119	2.626e-14

Pearson deltaTimePerception~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
0.0639029	0.1968780	0.1309796	0.0001407

Pearson abs(deltaTimePerception)~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.1258056	0.0090165	-0.0586620	0.0893